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ОБЗОРНЫЕ СТАТЬИ/ REVIEW ARTICLES/ADABIYOTLAR SHARHI

1.	Аляви А.Л., Аляви Б.А., Абдуллаев А.Х., Узокв Ж.К. Технологии искусственного интеллекта в кардиологии Alyavi A.L., Alyavi B.A., Abdullaev A.Kh., Uzokov D.K. Artificial intelligence technologies in cardiology Alyavi A.L., Alyavi B.A., Abdullayev A.X., Uzokov J.K. Kardiologiyada sun'iy intellekt texnologiyalari.....	10
2.	Арипов С.А., Ташкенбаева Э.Н., Хайдаров А.Х., Авазова Х.А., Кодиров Д.А., Адилова Д.Н. Особенности течения ишемической болезни сердца у больных ХОБЛ Aripov S.A., Tashkenbaeva E.N., Khaidarov A.Kh., Avazova Kh.A., Kodirov D.A., Adilova D.N. Features of the course of coronary heart disease in patients with COPD Aripov S.A., Tashkenbayeva E.N., Haydarov A.X. Avazova H.A., Kodirov D.A., Adilova D.N. O' SOK bilan og'rigan bemorlarda yurak ishemik kasalligi kechishining o' ziga xos xususiyatlari.....	15
3.	Кариева Х.И., Ибодуллаев С.И., Абдушукуров Р.П., Мансуров Ш.И., Намозов Д.Х. Особенности оказания первой медицинской помощи при удушье, остановке сердечно-легочной деятельности, отравлении и передозировке лекарств, сильном кровотечении, обмороке, судорогах и коме. Kariyeva X.I., Ibodullayev S.I., Abdushukurov R.P., Mansurov Sh.Y., Namozov D.X. Features of first aid in case of suffocation, cardiac arrest, poisoning and overdose of drugs, severe bleeding, fainting, convulsions and coma. Kariyeva X.I., Ibodullayev S.I., Abdushukurov R.P., Mansurov Sh.Y., Namozov D.X. Bo'g' ilish, yurak to'xtashi, zaharlanish va dorilarning haddan tashqari dozasi, og'ir qon ketishi, hushdan ketish, konvulsiyalar va komada birinchi yordamning xususiyatlari.....	21
ОРИГИНАЛЬНЫЕ СТАТЬИ/ ORIGINAL STATE/ ORIGINAL MAQOLALAR		
4.	Гурбанова С.Р., Бахшалиев А.Б. Изучение эпидемиологических особенностей пациентов с врожденными пороками сердца в Баку Qurbanova S.R., Bakhshaliev A.B. Study of epidemiological characteristics of patients with congenital heart defects in Baku Gurbanova S.R., Baxshaliev O.B. Bokuda tug'ma yurak nomuslari bo'lgan bemorlarning epidemiologik xususiyatlarini o'rganish.....	25
5.	Зиядуллаев Ш.Х., Исмаилов Ж.А., Расули Ф.О., Тураев Х.Н., Хамидуллаев Ф.Ф., Журакулов Ф.Н. Эффективность лечения пациентов с тяжелой формой бронхиальной астмой Ziyadullaev Sh.Kh., Ismailov J.A., Rasuli F.O., Turayev X.N., Xamidullaev F.F., Jurakulov F.N. Effectiveness of treatment of patients with severe bronchial asthma Ziyadullayev Sh.X., Ismoilov J.A., Rasuli F.O., Turayev X.N., Xamidullaev F.F., Juraqulov F.N. Og'ir bronxial astma bilan og'rigan bemorlarning davolash samaradorligi.....	30
6.	Исмаилов Дж.А., Хамраев Ф.Х., Хамидуллаев Ф.Ф., Расули Ф.О., Тураев Х.Н. Изучение клинической эффективности пероральных антикоагулянтов прямого действия у пациентов с мерцательной аритмией Ismailov J.A., Xamraev F.X., Xamidullaev F.F., Rasuli F.O., Turaev H.N. Study of the clinical efficacy of oral direct anticoagulants in patients with atrial fibrillation Ismoilov J.A., Xamrayev F.X., Xamidullaev F.F., Rasuli F.O., To'raev H.N. Hilpillovchi fibrilatsiyasi bo'lgan bemorlarda to'g'ridan-to'g'ri ta'sir qiluvchi peroral antikoagulyantlarining klinik samaradorligini o'rganish.....	35
7.	Исмаилов Д.А., Хамраев Ф.Х., Хамидуллаев Ф.Ф., Расули Ф.О., Тураев Х.Н. Особенности ремоделирования сердца у больных с хронической сердечной недостаточностью на фоне постинфарктного миокардиосклероза и дилатационной кардиомиопатии Ismailov J.A., Xamraev F.X., Xamidullaev F.F., Rasuli F.O., Turaev H.N. Features of heart remodeling in patients with chronic heart failure due to post-infarction myocardiosclerosis and dilated cardiomyopathy Ismoilov J.A., Xamrayev F.X., Xamidullaev F.F., Rasuli F.O., To'raev H.N. Infarktdan keyingi miyokardiyoskleroz va dilatatsion kardiomyopatiya fonida surunkali yurak etishmovchiligi bo'lgan bemorlarda yurakni qayta qurish xususiyatlari.....	39
8.	Киличев А.А., Ризаев Ж.А. Клиническая характеристика больных ишемической болезнью сердца, переведенных на санаторно-курортный этап реабилитации Qilichev A.A., Rizaev J.A. Clinical characteristics of patients with coronary heart disease transferred to sanatorium-resort stage of rehabilitation Qilichev A.A., Rizayev J.A. Reabilitatsiyaning sanatoriy bosqichiga o'tkazilgan yurak ishemik kasalligi bilan og'rigan bemorlarning klinik xususiyatlari.....	43
9.	Киличев А.А., Ризаев Ж.А. Оценка медикаментозного лечения больных ишемической болезнью сердца после коронарного шунтирования и его влияние на прогноз в долгосрочной перспективе Qilichev A.A., Rizaev J.A. Evaluation of drug treatment in patients with coronary heart disease after coronary artery bypass grafting and its effect on long-term prognosis Qilichev A.A., Rizayev J.A. Yurak ishemik kasalligi bo'lgan bemorlarda aksh dan keyin medikamentoz davolashni baholash va uning uzoq muddatli prognozga ta'siri.....	47

10	Лаханов А.О., Ташкенбаева Э.Н., Эргашев А.Ш. Время и особенности появления мерцательной аритмии у больных острым инфарктом миокарда различной локализации Lakhanov A.O., Tashkenbaeva E.N., Ergashev A.Sh. Time and features of appearance of an atrial fibrillation in patients with acute myocardial infarction of different locations Лаханов А.О., Ташкенбаева Э.Н., Эргашев А.Ш. Turli xil lokalizatsiyadagi o'tkir miokard infarkti bo'lgan bemorlarda bo'lmachalar fibrilatsiyaning paydo bo'lish vaqti va xususiyatlari.....	51
11	Маматкулова Ф.Х. Абдиев К.М. Махматов Ф.Э. Реабилитация железодефицитной анемии у больных с патологией органов пищеварения Mamatkulova F.X. Abdiyev K.M. Makhmatov F.E. Rehabilitation of iron deficiency anemia in patients with pathology of the gastrointestinal system Маматкулова Ф.Х. Абдиев К.М. Махматов Ф.Э. Ovqat hazm qilish tizimining patologiyasi mavjud bemorlarda temir tanqisligi kamqonligini reabilitatsiyasi.....	55
12	Муминов А. А., Матлубов М.М. Некоторые показатели эффективности центральных блокад при абдоминальном родоразрешении женщин с умеренно выраженным митральным стенозом Muminov A.A., Matlubov M.M. Some Indicators of the Effectiveness of Central Blocks in Abdominal Delivery of Women with Moderate Mitral Stenosis Муминов А.А., Матлубов М.М. O'rtacha ifodalangan mitral stenozli ayollarda kesarcha-kesish amaliyoti davrida markaziy bloklarni qo'llash samaradorligining ba'zi ko'rsatkichlari.....	60
13	Ризаев Ж.А., Мусаева О.Т. Совершенствование амбулаторной гериатрической медицинской помощи Rizayev J.A., Musaeva O.T. Improving outpatient geriatric care Ризаев Ж.А., Мусаева О.Т. Ambulatoriya sharoitida geriatrik tibbiy yordamni takomillashtirish.....	66
14	Ризаев Ж.А., Саидов М.А., Хасанжанова Ф.О. Оценка качества оказания высокотехнологичной медицинской помощи в самаркандской области со стороны семейных врачей поликлиник, кардиологов и терапевтов Rizayev J.A., Saidov M.A., Xasanjanova F.O. Assessment of the quality of high-tech medical care in the samarkand region by family doctors of polyclinics, cardiologists and therapists Ризаев Ж.А., Саидов М.А., Хасанжанова Ф.О. Oilaviv poliklinika vrachlari, kardiologlar va terapevtlar tomonidan samarqand viloyatidagi yuqori texnologiyali tibbiy yordam sifatini baholanishi.....	69
15	Хамраев Ф.Х., Исмаилов Дж.А., Расули Ф.О., Хамидуллаев Ф.Ф., Камалов А.И. Изменение качества жизни больных с хронической обструктивной болезнью легких после применения биорегуляторных препаратов Xamraev F.X., Ismailov J.A., Rasuli F.O., Xamidullaev F.F., Kamalov A.I. Changes in the quality of life of patients with chronic obstructive pulmonary disease after the use of bioregulatory drugs Хамраев Ф.Х., Исмаилов Дж.А., Расули Ф.О., Хамидуллаев Ф.Ф., Камалов А.И. Bioregulyatsion dorilarni qo'llaganidan keyin surunkali obstruktiv o'pka kasalligi bo'lgan bemorlarning hayot sifatining o'zgarishi.....	77
16	Хамраев Ф.Х., Исмаилов Дж.А., Расули Ф.О., Хамидуллаев Ф.Ф., Камалов А.И. Особенности иммунного ответа пациентов с ишемической болезнью сердца при внебольничной пневмонии Xamraev F.X., Ismailov J.A., Rasuli F.O., Xamidullaev F.F., Kamalov A.I. Features of the immune response of patients with ischaemic heart disease in community-acquired pneumonia Хамраев Ф.Х., Исмаилов Дж.А., Расули Ф.О., Хамидуллаев Ф.Ф., Камалов А.И. Yurak qon tomir kasalliklari bilan o'g'rigan bemorlar shifoxonadan tashqari zotiljamga chalinganda ularning immun xolatining xususiyatlari.....	81
17	Шоалимова З.М., Нуритдинова Н.Б., Шодиева Г.Р. Особенности течения, лечения и прогноза острого коронарного синдрома без подъема сегмента ST у пациентов с железодефицитной анемией Shoalimova Z.M., Nuritdinova N.B., Shodieva G.R. Peculiarities of clinical course, treatment and prognostication of acute coronary syndrome without ST segment elevation in patients with iron deficiency anemia Шоалимова З.М., Нуритдинова Н.Б., Шодиева Г.Р. Temir tanqis anemiyasi bo'lgan bemorlarda ST segmentini elevatsiyasiz o'tkir koronar sindromning kechishi, davolash va prognozlash xususiyatlari.....	86

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ЭФФЕКТИВНОСТЬ ЛЕЧЕНИЯ ПАЦИЕНТОВ С ТЯЖЕЛОЙ ФОРМОЙ БРОНХИАЛЬНОЙ АСТМОЙ

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АННОТАЦИЯ

По последним данным, достигнут большой прогресс в лечении бронхиальной астмы. Эти результаты связаны с высокой эффективностью ингаляционных кортикостероидов при местной диагностике и патогенетическом лечении БА. Но, несмотря на достигнутые результаты, борьба с этим заболеванием продолжается. У больных с тяжелой формой БА ингаляционные кортикостероиды более эффективны при их совместном применении с β_2 -агонистами. Почти каждый второй больной бронхиальной астмой страдает ночными приступами. Большинство больных не могут вести активный образ жизни. Многие пациенты вынуждены обращаться к врачу в связи с обострением и развитием заболевания.

Ключевые слова: бронхиальная астма, будесонид, преднизолон, небулайзер

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EFFECTIVENESS OF TREATMENT OF PATIENTS WITH SEVERE BRONCHIAL ASTHMA**ANNOTATION**

Recent data show that significant advances have been made in the treatment of bronchial asthma. These results are associated with the high efficacy of inhaled corticosteroids in the local diagnosis and etiological treatment of asthma. However, despite these gains, the fight against the disease continues. For patients with severe BA, inhaled corticosteroids are more effective when combined with β_2 agonists. Almost every second person with bronchial asthma suffers from nighttime attacks. Most patients are unable to lead an active lifestyle. Many patients require medical attention as the disease worsens or progresses.

Keywords: bronchial asthma, budesonide, prednisolone, nebulizer

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OG'IR BRONXIAL ASTMA BILAN OG'RIGAN BEMORLARNING DAVOLASH SAMARADORLIGI**ANNOTATSIIYA**

Oxirgi ma'lumotlarga ko'ra bronxial astmani davolashda ko'zga ko'rinarli yutuqlarga erishildi. Bu natijalar BAning topikal diagnostikasi va patogenetik davolashda ingalyatsion steroidlarning sezilarli samaradorligi bilan bog'liq. Ammo erishilgan natijalarga qaramay, ushbu kasallikka qarshi kurash qoniqarli emas. Og'ir BA bilan kasallangan bemorlarda ingalyatsion steroidlar, β_2 -agonistlar bilan birgalikda qo'llanilganda samaraliroq bo'ladi. Astma bilan kasallangan deyarli har ikkinchi bemor tungi hujumlardan qiynaladi. Bemorlarning aksariyat qismi faol jismoniy faoliyatini yo'qotgan. Ko'pgina bemorlar kasallikning kuchayishi va rivojlanishi tufayli shifokorga murojat qilishga majbur bo'lishadi.

Kalit so'zlar: og'ir bronxial astma, budesonid, prednizolon, nebulayzer, davolash

The relevance of the topic: Corticosteroids are one of the most effective drugs in the treatment of bronchial asthma because they also effectively reduce the number of asthma attacks [2,15]. Inhaled corticosteroids bind to special receptors in the cytoplasm, activate them, form complexes, then enter the cell nucleus, bind to DNA and interact with key enzymes, receptors and Transcriptional mechanism of other protein complexes. This results in a pharmacological and therapeutic effect.

Disadvantages of inhaled systemic corticosteroids during asthma attacks are late effects and the risk of side effects. The effect of systemic corticosteroid treatment begins after 5-10 hours, so patients with bronchial asthma should prescribe it early [1,4,20].

Breathed in glucocorticosteroids (IGCS) decrease the blend of prostaglandins, counting anti-inflammatory cytokines and leukotrienes; diminish in capillary porousness (stabilization of organic films, driving to the advancement of an exudative impact). Breathed in glucocorticosteroids stabilize lysosomal films, diminish the discharge

of proteolytic chemicals from lysosomes, and anticipate the advancement of damaging forms in tissues. Breathed in glucocorticosteroids upgrade the blend of anti-inflammatory proteins (lipocortin-1), upgrade apoptosis and decrease the number of eosinophils by restraining interleukin-5. Breathed in corticosteroids increment the solidness of cell films, diminish vascular porousness, make strides the movement of β -receptors, synthesize unused ones and increment their affectability, invigorate epithelial cells [3,8,9].

Nebulizer corticosteroid treatment for hormone-dependent asthma has been well examined in a few considers decreasing the measurements of systemic corticosteroids and essentially decrease side impacts [6,7,19]. The part of IGCS in worsening bronchial asthma is right now the cause of various debate and talks. In spite of the fact that the anti-inflammatory impact of IGCS shows itself after actuation of systemic corticosteroid receptors and a long cascade of consequent biochemical responses, IGCS have a coordinate impact on the bronchial mucosa, coming about in a speedier clinical impact [10,14,17]. The combination of IGCS with β 2-agonists features a more noteworthy broncholytic impact than monotherapy with β 2-agonists. With compounding of bronchial asthma, the impact of IGCS is watched after 1.5-2 hours [12,16]. Be that as it may, the properties of budesonide (great dissolvability in water) have a positive impact on the useful parameters

of breath after 1 hour and on the markers of irritation after 3-4 hours [11].

As of now, there are a few thinks about of the impact of nebulizer treatment with corticosteroids on the compounding of bronchial asthma [13,18]. A few ponders appear that budesonide nebulizer therapy is as successful as verbal corticosteroids within the treatment of asthma exacerbations.

The purpose of the study

There was a ponder of the adequacy of the utilize of corticosteroids (through a nebulizer with budesonide) within the treatment of bronchial asthma.

Materials and methods

Over the past 2 a long time, perception was carried out in 105 patients hospitalized within the office of pulmonology due to intense assaults of bronchial asthma. The patients were analyzed based on clinical criteria, such as the nearness of forceful hack and shortness of breath, the nearness of wheezing from a far distance, a history of sensitivities and hereditary inclination. The determination is affirmed by common clinical studies, assurance of the entire level of IgE within the blood and the comes about of spirographic examination. In 93% of patients (98 patients) bronchial asthma was analyzed prior, and in 7% (8 patients) bronchial asthma was analyzed for the primary time.

Distribution of hospitalized patients with acute asthma attack by age and gender

Table 1

Gender	20-24 years	25-29 years	30-34 years	35-39 years	40-45 years
Male	8 (6,3 %)	9 (7,5 %)	11 (8,9 %)	16 (13,2)	17 (16,4 %)
Female	5 (3,7 %)	6 (6,4 %)	13 (10,5 %)	11 (2,6 %)	15 (14,4 %)

Depending on the seriousness of the asthma assault, patients are isolated into:

intemetic 12 (11.4%), gentle diligent 38 (36.2%), medium determined 42 (40%), serious diligent 13 (12.4%).

The seriousness of the assault was evaluated in agreement with the proposals for the treatment of bronchial asthma, taking into consideration such clinical pointers as respiratory rate, heart rate, enthusiastic state of the understanding, physical action, support of assistant respiratory muscles, auscultative changes. Oxygen immersion of the blood.

85 (81%) patients were taken to the clinic by rescue vehicle, and the remaining 20 (19%) looked for offer assistance on their claim. The dispersion of bronchial asthma by seriousness is as takes after: gentle - 15 (14.3%), medium - 62 (59%), serious - 28 (26.7%).

In 35 (33.3%) patients, compounding of asthma with an assault was caused by bacterial and viral contaminations. In the event that these

patients have inebriation disorder at the same time with asthma assaults, a common blood test uncovers leukocytosis. In 45 (43%) patients, suspension of breathed in medicines without a doctor's authorization driven to an increment in asthma assaults. In 25 (23.7%) patients, the term and number of seizures expanded as a result of contact with allergens.

Patients with a serious asthma assault did not get satisfactory anti-inflammatory treatment and cannot be classified as a gather of patients with "controlled asthma". 8 (7.6%) patients with direct to serious asthma gotten sodium cromoglycate as essential treatment, whereas 18 (17%) patients gotten uncontrolled breathed in corticosteroids. In 23 (21.9%) patients, the causative operator was an worsening of bronchial hindrance against the foundation of viral contaminations of the upper respiratory tract, particularly within the elderly.

We taken after the calculation appeared in Figure 1 to halt an asthma assault.

To eliminate an acute attack of bronchial asthma, a therapy algorithm is used.

Table 2

Rapid action of bronchodilator (berodual)	
Positive reaction	Insufficient response
Inhalation of a bronchodilator every 1-3 hours, continued inhalation with high doses (inhalation by doses)	Continue to inhale the bronchodilator every 20 minutes for an hour
Positive reaction	Insufficient response
Inhalation of a bronchodilator every 1-3 hours, continued inhalation with high doses (inhalation by doses)	Oral administration of prednisone or budesonide via a nebulizer with repeated inhalations of a bronchodilator
Positive reaction	Insufficient response
Continue inhaling bronchodilators every 1-3 hours while continuing to inhale high doses of corticosteroids.	Intravenous administration of prednisone, oxygenotherapy, bronchodilator spraying, repeated infusion of aminophyllin every 30 minutes
Positive reaction	Insufficient response
Oral prednisone or budesonide tablet using a nebulizer, bronchodilator nebulizer every 1-4 hours, oxygen therapy	Carrying out resuscitation measures
Positive response	
Reduction of respiratory rate by bronchodilators	

A nebulizer with a compressor was utilized for inward breath. Berodual is endorsed 20-25 drops. To avoid compounding of bronchial obstacle, it is vital to break up the restorative substance (up to 2 ml) with water, and not with isotonic sodium chloride arrangement [15]. The term of inward breath is 8-10 minutes.

At that point, on the off chance that vital, these patients were given a bronchodilator within the shape of a metered-dose inward breath frame measured through a separator for essential treatment.

These patients are separated into 2 groups. 28 patients of the primary bunch also gotten prednisone orally at a dosage of 0.5 to 1 mg / kg / day for 3 days. Thirty-two patients within the moment gather gotten budesonide at a dose of 2 mg twice a day through a nebulizer.

The primary bunch incorporates patients with an expanded hazard of antagonistic results: patients with hormone-dependent bronchial asthma, patients with a history of asthma, patients with expanded volatility with fear of passing. Too included are patients who have looked for offer assistance when the term of an crisis assault surpasses 48 hours.

Research results

The condition of patients in both bunches stabilized after 14 hours and made strides altogether after 24 hours. After 72 hours, as it were some patients created a dry hasty on the foundation of a slight prolongation of breathing time.

Table 3

Dynamics of upper respiratory tract flow in patients of the first and second groups (% of the corresponding value)				
Time period	First group n=33	Second group n=20	Student's t criterion	p
Early	42,9±4,0	45,2±3,8	1,895	>0,05
After 24 hours	56,4±3,1	60,2±4,4	1,948	>0,05
After 48 hours	68,1±2,5	72,6±3,25	3,275	<0,05

Table 4

Clinical efficacy of treatment in the first and second groups of patients												
Clinical signs	First group -prednisone n=26					Second group budesonid n=28						
	Before treatment	12	24	36	48	72	After treatment	12	24	36	48	72
Shortness of breath	24	23	9	2	1	0	20	19	11	8	2	1
Tachycardia	24	24	10	4	2	1	20	18	10	4	2	1
Weakness	24	17	7	1	0	0	20	14	6	4	3	1
Irritability	20	4	0	0	0	0	15	2	0	0	0	0
Limited speech	24	2	0	0	0	0	17	2	1	0	0	0
Participation of auxiliary muscles in breathing	24	20	8	1	1	0	20	9	3	1	0	0
Chest bulging	24	22	12	3	3	1	20	16	9	2	0	0
Weakened breathing	24	22	7	3	2	0	20	20	6	6	4	0
Prolongation of the exhalation cycle	24	24	18	15	8	1	20	14	8	6	2	0

1-drawing.

Dynamics of severity (by average score) of clinical symptoms (by hours) in patients with bronchial asthma of the first (prednisone, blue bar) of the second group during treatment.

The seriousness of clinical signs was taken into consideration each 12 hours amid corticosteroid treatment. Crest blood stream estimations were examined and assessed independently as it were in middle-aged patients (Table 3). The flow of clinical indications are displayed in Table 4 and Figure 1.

The elements of clinical markers and a tall stream of exhalation show the viability of both plans of corticosteroid treatment. When comparing the dynamics of clinical side effects within the two bunches, an enhancement ought to be famous within the bunch of patients receiving budesonide suspension amid the primary 12 hours, and a essentially higher change within the bunch accepting budesonide suspension with a most extreme exhalation rate after 48 hours. Given the particular subjectivity of the evaluation of clinical indications, it can be famous that the viability of prednisone (in tablets) and budesonide (in a nebulizer arrangement) is comparable. The normal term of

treatment with systemic corticosteroids was 3.8 days. Systemic side impacts and nebulizer stabilization, patients were exchanged to breathed in corticosteroids (Fluticasone, budesonide) in two dosages.

Conclusions:

1. Inward breath of budesonide in combination with B2 agonists through a nebulizer is successful for the treatment of patients with direct and extreme asthma assaults.
2. Budesonide has been found to have higher clinical adequacy compared to systemic corticosteroids.
3. Early organization of systemic corticosteroids is shown in patients with serious asthma and chance of passing.
4. With the combined utilize of breathed in corticosteroids and B2-agonists, the length of asthma assaults is decreased, and the quality of life of patients is altogether moved forward.

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